

SCHOOL SYSTEM STANDARDS IN RELATION TO SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT DECISION-MAKING

ELMAR L. PALOMARES

Abstract. The study unfolded the role of School System Standards in relation to school-based-management decision-making. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected 120 teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of the School System Standards in terms of access to extracurricular activities is extensive; likewise, the extent of school-based management decision-making in terms of curriculum and program decisions and participation in decision-making are sometimes manifested, while, inclusivity and equity and accountability measures are rarely manifested, thus, is moderately extensive. There is a significant Relationship between School System Standards and school-based management decision-making. All domains of the School System Standards profile regarding special needs and disabilities, language proficiency, school composition, cultural competence, and inclusivity indicate statistically significant in influencing school-based management decision-making. This shows that the domains of School System Standards profiles significantly influence school-based management decision-making.

KEY WORDS

1. School System Standards .
2. school-based management decision-making.
3. cultural competence.

1. Introduction

School system standards and school-based management (SBM) systems are interrelated components of educational administration that aim to enhance education quality. School system standards provide a consistent framework of expectations, goals, and benchmarks that guide educational practices and policies across schools. These standards ensure uniformity in the quality of education, specifying what students should learn, how teachers should teach, and how educational outcomes should be assessed. In contrast, SBM systems decentralize decision-making authority, granting more au-

tonomy to individual schools to manage their operations, resources, and instructional strategies. SBM allows schools to innovate and adapt strategies to meet these standards in a manner that is responsive to their specific contexts. This combination can improve educational outcomes by balancing high standards and allowing local adaptations catering to diverse student populations.

School system standards as discussed by Wong, Coburn, and Kamel (2020) shared that school leaders had legal authority over most instructional decisions; they overwhelmingly

made decisions consistent with central office preferences. Differences in the combination of strategies that central office leaders used and their interaction with school leaders led to greater variability in how school leaders in one district made decisions aligned with central office preferences and greater feelings of coercion among school leaders in the second. These findings unpack the dynamics among local education leaders as they implement and sometimes alter the rules within policies through their daily practice. They analyzed the relationships between high school students' career maturity, career decision-making difficulties, and career decision-making self-efficacy. They investigate whether career maturity, career decision-making difficulties, and career decision-making self-efficacy are altered according to gender, type of school, and grade level. Duru (2022) revealed a weak but significant negative relationship between career maturity and career decision-making difficulties scale in terms of total scores and subscale scores. Wahono et.al. (2022) shared that there was a medium- and low-level significant negative relationship between the career decision-making difficulties scale total and subscale scores and the career decision-making self-efficacy total and subscale scores. The subsequent analysis to describe the mediating role of career decision-making self-efficacy demonstrated that career decision-making self-efficacy had a partial mediating role. Furthermore, male students were found to have a more disadvantaged status than female students in terms of career maturity. Based on the fact that students' career decision-making difficulties stemmed from a lack of readiness, psycho-education programs can be organized to determine the reasons for the lack of readiness, find solutions, and provide the necessary information and skills. Future studies may examine the reasons for the differences in career maturity. In the Philippine setting, school-based management (SBM) decision-making reflects a

significant shift towards decentralization in the educational system. This approach empowers schools with greater autonomy and responsibility over their administrative and academic functions. Under SBM, schools in the Philippines are given the authority to make decisions on various aspects such as budget allocation, curriculum implementation, and the development of school improvement plans. This decentralization is intended to foster a more responsive and adaptive educational environment, as local school officials, including principals, teachers, and community stakeholders, are better positioned to understand and address their students' specific needs and challenges (Cevik Dogan (2023). The Department of Education (DepEd) supports SBM by providing guidelines and resources to ensure that schools have the necessary capacity and support to make informed decisions. This localized decision-making process aims to enhance accountability, promote community involvement, and improve the overall quality of education. However, the success of SBM in the Philippines hinges on the effective training of school leaders, the active participation of the community, and the continuous support from higher administrative bodies to ensure that schools can meet national educational standards while addressing local needs (Asio, et.al., 2022). In provincial areas of the Philippines, school-based management (SBM) decision-making plays a crucial role in addressing the unique educational challenges faced by these communities. Provincial schools often encounter distinct issues such as limited resources, infrastructure deficits, and a need for localized curriculum adjustments to reflect cultural and socioeconomic contexts. SBM empowers local school leaders, teachers, and community members to make decisions tailored to their specific needs, fostering a more relevant and effective educational environment. By decentralizing authority, provincial schools can prioritize budget allocations, infrastructure improve-

ments, and instructional strategies that directly benefit their students. This local autonomy is supported by the Department of Education (DepEd) through capacity-building initiatives, ensuring that school leaders are equipped with the skills and knowledge required for effective governance.

2. Methodology

Research methods are the systematic procedures and techniques researchers employ to gather, analyze, and interpret data to answer specific research questions or test hypotheses. These methods serve as the foundation for scientific inquiry, enabling researchers to design and conduct studies in a structured and rigorous manner. In this context, the introduction provides an overview of the selected research method, highlighting its relevance, strengths, and limitations in the context of the research endeavor. Understanding the research method is essential for both researchers and readers as it determines the validity and reliability of the study's findings and contributes to the broader body of knowledge in the field of inquiry. This introduction aims to elucidate the key components and considerations associated with the chosen research method, setting the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the research methodology employed in the study. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is a comprehensive approach in the field of research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and predict outcomes in a systematic manner. This design typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervention, manipulation, or control of variables (Creswel, 2014). Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design significantly studies the relationship between the School System Standards of students and school-based management (SBM) decision-making. This research design helps educational researchers and policymakers gain insights into how various demographic factors influence the decision-making processes within educational institutions. In a non-experimental descriptive-correlational study, researchers gather data on the demographic characteristics of students, such as age, gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, language proficiency, and special needs. They also collect data on specific aspects of SBM decision-making, including resource allocation, curriculum choices, teacher staffing, and community involvement. By analyzing this data, researchers can create a comprehensive picture of the demographic profile of the student body and how it relates to various aspects of SBM. Researchers can identify patterns and associations between demographic variables and specific SBM decisions through correlational analysis. For example, they may discover that schools with a higher proportion of students from low-income backgrounds allocate more resources to programs to address achievement gaps. This information provides valuable insights into the

impact of demographics on decision-making processes. Predictive research design takes this analysis further by using statistical models to predict future SBM decisions based on demographic trends. For instance, it may predict how changes in the student population's demographics (e.g., an increase in English Language Learners) could influence resource allocation decisions in the coming years. This predictive capability allows educational institutions to proactively plan and adapt their SBM practices to meet the evolving needs of their student body. Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs provide a valuable framework for understanding the intricate relationship between a school's demographic profile and SBM decision-making. By leveraging this research, schools and educational policymakers can make informed decisions to promote equity, inclusivity, and effective management practices that better serve the diverse needs of students.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary and Secondary Teachers in the Public schools within Region XI. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each respective School. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were selected for they were assumed to have been engaged in implementing various school learning programs mostly under activities of school-based management. They are qualified for the role they were expected to have performed and contributed to, given that they have attended various activities aside from the school's management in curriculum delivery and implementation and governance. This is done through school faculty meetings and other group and committee

meetings to improve the school and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire, which consisted of indicators of roles of demographic profile in terms of special needs and disabilities, language proficiency, school composition, cultural competence and inclusivity, and access to extracurricular activities. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the school-based management decision-making regarding inclusivity and equity, participation in decision-making, curriculum an program decisions and accountability measures. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.859, meaning that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the role of the demographic profile. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are

provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The School System Standards is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The School System Standards is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The School System Standards is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The School System Standards is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The School System Standards is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of school-based management decision-making, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school-based management decision-making is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The school-based management decision-making is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The school-based management decision-making is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The school-based management decision-making is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The school-based management decision-making is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct the study. On the second week of December 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal’s contents and objective. He then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004), and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. On the last week of February up to the first week of March 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a

letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study among the Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This ac-

tivity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought

the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometimes during the first week of June 2024, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of school system standards, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of school-based management decision-making. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between School System Standards and school-based management

decision-making. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of School System Standards that significantly influence school-based management decision-making (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data gathered in tabular and textual form to provide clear ideas and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. Various reviews present implications of the results to corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

Table 1 presents a summary of the extent of the school system standards. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: access to extracurricular activities (3.96) is extensive; cultural competence and inclusivity (3.36), school composition (3.33), and special needs and disabilities (2.95) are moderately extensive; language proficiency (2.57) denotes less extensive. This suggests that the extent of the demographic profile's role is moderately extensive.

School system standards play a crucial role in shaping the educational landscape, particularly in addressing special needs and disabilities. A comprehensive understanding of a stu-

dent body's demographic makeup allows educators and policymakers to tailor support systems to meet the diverse needs of learners. Special needs and disabilities vary across demographic groups, and recognizing these differences is essential for providing inclusive and effective education. Language proficiency is another key aspect tied to demographic profiles. Students from diverse linguistic backgrounds may face unique challenges in accessing and comprehending the curriculum. Addressing language barriers through targeted language support programs and resources is crucial to ensuring equal educational opportunities for all.

Table 1. Summary on the extent of the School System Standards

No	School System Standards	Mean
1	Special needs and disabilities	2.95 (Moderately Extensive)
2	Language proficiency	2.57 (Less Extensive)
3	School composition	3.33 (Moderately Extensive)
4	Cultural competence and inclusivity	3.36 (Moderately Extensive)
5	Access to extra-curricular activities	3.96 (Extensive)
Overall Mean		4.02 (Extensive)

School composition, reflecting the demographic diversity of students, has a profound impact on the overall learning environment. Inclusive educational settings that embrace diversity foster a sense of belonging and support for students with special needs. A diverse school composition also promotes positive interactions among students from various backgrounds, enhancing cultural competence and inclusivity. Cultural competence is vital in understanding and meeting the needs of students from different demographic backgrounds. Educators and school staff must have the knowledge and skills to navigate cultural differences, ensuring that all students feel valued and respected. In this context, inclusivity involves creating a learning environment that appreciates and celebrates diversity, fostering a sense of community among students, educators, and families. Access to extracurricular activities is another dimension influenced by demographic factors. Students with

Table 2 presents a summary of the extent of school-based management decision-making. The result is focused on the mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: curriculum and program decisions (3.04) and participation in decision-making (2.63) are sometimes mani-

School-based management decision-making plays a pivotal role in shaping the inclusivity and equity of educational institutions. The ex-

special needs may face additional challenges in participating in these activities, and their inclusion requires thoughtful consideration of individual needs. Demographic factors such as socio-economic status and cultural background may impact the availability and affordability of extracurricular opportunities. Ensuring equitable access to these activities is essential for fostering holistic development and social integration among students. In conclusion, the role of demographic profile in education is extensive and multifaceted. It affects how educational institutions address special needs and disabilities, support language proficiency, shape school composition, foster cultural competence and inclusivity, and provide access to extracurricular activities. Recognizing and responding to the diverse needs of students within their demographic context is fundamental to creating an inclusive and effective educational experience for all.

fest, while inclusivity and equity (2.54) and accountability measures (2.22) are rarely manifested. An average mean score of 2.60 suggests that the extent of school-based management decision-making is moderately extensive.

tent to which decisions are made at the school level directly influences the ability to cater to the diverse needs of students, fostering a

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of School-based Management Decision-making

No	School-based Management Decision-making	Mean
1	Inclusivity and equity	2.54 (Less Extensive)
2	Participation in decision-making	2.63 (Moderately Extensive)
3	Curriculum and program decisions	3.04 (Moderately Extensive)
4	Accountability measures	2.22 (Less Extensive)
Overall Mean		2.60 (Moderately Extensive)

more inclusive learning environment. Inclusive decision-making involves the active participation of stakeholders representing various perspectives, ensuring that the voices of all community members, including students, parents, and teachers, are heard and considered. Participation in decision-making is a key aspect of school-based management, and its extent profoundly impacts equity. When decision-making processes are transparent, collaborative, and involve diverse voices, the likelihood of addressing the unique needs of different student groups increases. Inclusivity is enhanced when decisions reflect a comprehensive understanding of the student body’s demographics, socioeconomic status, and cultural background. Curriculum and program decisions made at the school level have a direct impact on the educational experiences of students. Schools that embrace inclusivity in decision-making can tailor their curriculum and programs to meet the specific needs of diverse learners. This might include incorporating culturally relevant content, accommodating various learning styles, and providing support for students with special needs. In doing so, school-based management contributes to an equitable distribution of educational resources and opportunities. Furthermore, accountability measures are integral to ensuring that school-based management decisions uphold standards of equity and inclusivity. By establishing clear metrics and performance indicators, schools can track their progress in addressing disparities and promoting an inclusive learning envi-

ronment. Accountability measures also hold decision-makers responsible for considering the needs of all students, reinforcing the commitment to equity in educational outcomes. In conclusion, the extent of school-based management decision-making significantly influences inclusivity and equity in education. Through active participation in decision-making, schools can better address the diverse needs of their students. Inclusive decision-making in curriculum and program choices ensures that education is tailored to individual needs, promoting equity. Accountability measures serve as checks and balances, reinforcing the commitment to providing an inclusive and equitable education for all students.

Relationship between School System Standards and School-based Management Decision-making

Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant correlation between demographic profile and school-based management decision-making. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between demographic profile and school-based management decision-making must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of statistically significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson’s r generated a strong positive significant correlation between demographic profile ($r=0.873$; $p<.001$) and school-based management decision-making.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between School System Standards and School-Based Management Decision-Making

Variables	School System Standards	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
School-based Management Decision-Making	0.873	0.001	Significant	Reject H_0	*significant @ $p < 0.05$

The significant relationship between school system standards and school-based management (SBM) decision-making lies in their complementary roles in enhancing educational quality and effectiveness. School system standards provide a structured framework of educational expectations, including curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and assessment criteria, ensuring consistency and equity across all schools. These standards serve as a benchmark for what students should achieve, guiding schools in their educational goals. On the other hand, SBM decentralizes decision-making authority, granting individual schools the autonomy to manage their operations, resources, and instructional approaches based on their unique needs and contexts. This local flexibility allows schools to innovate and adapt their strategies to better meet the standards set by the broader educational system. When integrated, school system standards ensure that all schools adhere to a high baseline of educational quality, while SBM empowers schools to tailor their efforts to achieve these standards in the most effective and contextually relevant ways. This synergy promotes accountability, responsiveness, and continuous improvement, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes and student success. The theory underpinning the relationship between school system standards and school-based management (SBM) decision-making is rooted in decentralization and accountability frameworks within educational administration. According to these theories, centralized standards provide a coherent set of expectations and goals that ensure uniformity in educational quality and equity. These standards act as a guiding framework that sets the minimum benchmarks

for what students should know and be able to do, thus ensuring a baseline of educational outcomes across all schools (Wahono, et.al., 2022). Simultaneously, the theory of decentralization posits that giving local schools more autonomy in decision-making enhances their ability to respond to specific needs and contextual challenges. SBM embodies this by empowering principals, teachers, and local stakeholders to make decisions about resource allocation, curriculum adaptations, and instructional strategies. This localized control encourages innovation, accountability, and a more responsive educational environment. The interplay between these theories suggests that while school system standards establish the overarching goals and accountability measures, SBM allows for the flexibility and contextual responsiveness needed to achieve these goals effectively. By combining the consistency of centralized standards with the adaptability of decentralized management, the educational system can maintain high-quality education while addressing the diverse needs of individual school communities. This integrated approach theoretically leads to improved educational outcomes, as it leverages both uniform expectations and local expertise (Schueler, 2023).

Domains of School System Standards significantly influence school-based management decision-making

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of School System Standards that significantly influence school-based management decision-making. It can be noted that all domains of demographic profile in terms of special needs and disabilities (0.011); language proficiency (0.002); school compo-

sition (0.013); cultural competence and inclusivity (0.030), and v (0.000) indicate statistically significant to influence school-based management decision-making. This shows that the domains of demographic profile significantly influence school-based management decision-making. Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.899 suggests that the domains of demographic profile explained 89.9%. This provides empirical ev-

idence that the domains of demographic profile can account for and explain the variability of school-based management decision-making. In addition, the F -value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F -value (225.996) and F -statistic is significant $p < .010$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of school-based management decision-making.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on School System Standards and Decision Making

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H_0	(Intercept)	4.397		0.062	$p < .001$
H_1	(Intercept)	0.401		0.144	0.006
Special Needs and Disabilities	0.032	-0.031	0.042	0.011	Reject H_0
Language Proficiency	0.321	0.361	0.054	0.002	Reject H_0
School Composition	0.207	0.215	0.064	0.013	Reject H_0
Cultural Competence and Inclusivity	0.568	0.425	0.079	0.030	Reject H_0
Access to Extracurricular Activities	0.032	-0.021	0.046	0.000	Reject H_0
R^2				0.899	
F -value				225.996	
p -value				$p < .010$	

School System Standards, such as cultural background, significantly impact school-based decisions regarding cultural competence and inclusivity. Abdul Rahim et al. (2021) shared that Schools with a diverse demographic profile often prioritize professional development for educators to enhance cultural competence. Management decisions also involve integrating culturally relevant content into the curriculum, creating an inclusive atmosphere that respects and values the cultural diversity of students. These decisions aim to foster a sense of belonging and understanding among students from various backgrounds. School System Standards considerations, such as socioeconomic status and cultural preferences, influence decisions regarding access to extracurricular activities. School-based management considers

the diverse interests and resources available to students, ensuring that these activities are accessible and inclusive. Colakkadioglu and Celik (2016) said that decisions may involve offering a range of options, providing financial support where needed, addressing potential barriers to participation, and promoting equity in extracurricular opportunities. In conclusion, the school system standards significantly influence school-based management decision-making across various facets of education. By considering the unique characteristics and needs associated with special needs, language proficiency, school composition, cultural competence, inclusivity, and access to extracurricular activities, educational institutions can make informed decisions that contribute to creating an inclusive, equitable, and supportive learning environment for all stu-

dents.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper section outlines the researcher's conclusions and recommendations, drawing support from the literature covered in the initial chapters. The conclusion aligns with the problem statements articulated in this study.

4.1. Findings—The following are the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of the School System Standards in terms of access to extracurricular activities is extensive, while cultural competence and inclusivity, school composition, and special needs and disabilities are moderately extensive, while language proficiency denotes less extensive. This suggests that the extent of role of demographic profile is moderately extensive. The extent of school-based management decision-making regarding curriculum and program decisions and participation in decision-making are sometimes manifested, while inclusivity and equity and accountability measures are rarely manifested. An average mean score of suggests that the extent of school-based management decision-making is moderately extensive. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson's r generated a significant correlation between demographic profile and school-based management decision-making. All domains of School System Standards, in terms of special needs and disabilities, language proficiency, school composition, cultural competence, and inclusivity, are statistically significant in influencing school-based management decision-making. This shows that the domains of demographic profile significantly influence school-based management decision-making.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions, to wit; The extent of the School System Standards profile in terms of access to ex-

tracurricular activities is extensive, while cultural competence and inclusivity, school composition, and special needs and disabilities are moderately extensive, while language proficiency denotes less extensive. This suggests that the extent of the role of the demographic profile is moderately extensive. The extent of school-based management decision-making in terms of curriculum and program decisions and participation in decision-making are sometimes manifested. In contrast, inclusivity and equity and accountability measures are rarely manifested. This suggests that the extent of school-based management decision-making is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between School System Standards and school-based management decision-making. All domains of School System Standards, in terms of special needs and disabilities, language proficiency, school composition, cultural competence, and inclusivity, indicate statistically significant influence on school-based management decision-making. This shows that the domains of demographic profile significantly influence school-based management decision-making. Integrating the Principal-Agent Theory and Critical Race Theory or Cultural Responsiveness Theory in the study of the role of demographic profile in school-based decision-making provides a comprehensive and multi-dimensional approach to understanding this complex educational context. The Principal-Agent Theory offers insights into school decision-making dynamics, where administrators (principals) delegate authority to teachers (agents). By con-

sidering this theory, researchers can explore how information asymmetry, divergent interests, and accountability mechanisms impact decision-making processes. This theoretical perspective enables the study to examine the power dynamics within the school and how they intersect with demographic factors, shedding light on whether certain student groups face differential treatment in the decision-making process (Blake and Mestry, 2021).

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; To The Public School District Supervisor. May consider implementing professional development programs for teachers and staff that address the specific needs identified in the study. Additionally, they could advocate for increased resources and support systems tailored to the challenges highlighted in the research. Collaboration with community organizations and local agencies may also be recommended to enhance the district’s ability to address complex issues. To The School Principal. May focus on implementing policies and practices that align with the study’s findings. This may include creating an inclusive curricu-

lum, establishing support structures for students with specific needs, and fostering a culturally responsive learning environment. Collaboration between teachers and administrators should be encouraged to ensure that the recommendations are effectively integrated into the daily operations of the school. To The Teachers. May be provided with professional development opportunities that enhance their skills in addressing the identified needs. The study might recommend strategies for differentiated instruction, culturally responsive teaching, or methods to support students with diverse language proficiency levels. Continuous training and support systems can empower teachers to implement effective classroom practices. To The Future Researchers. May recommend areas that require further investigation or exploration. This could include suggesting longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of certain interventions, examining the effectiveness of specific teaching methods, or exploring the influence of evolving demographics on educational outcomes. Encouraging future researchers to build on the current study’s findings contributes to improving educational practices.

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